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Study on The Thyroxine Administration and Ponderal Index (K) Relationship on Post-embryonic Development in *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.)

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Abstract

Thyroxine treatment given to the newly hatched larvae of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) for about one month and revealed faster post-embryonic development which is correlated with growth as against the control experiments. 75mg/lit. dose of thyroxine proved suitable in all respect. Mortality figure comes out 4,5,7 and 12 for 0.0mg/lit., 75mg/lit., 100mg/lit. and 125mg/lit. dose treatment respectively. The study revealed that there was a close relationship between growth and development. There is a very important aspect of Morpho-metrical parameters showed marked changes in all thyroxine hormone treated experiment (Cultural investigation). Study suggests that most powerful hormone therapy may prove in the culture of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.)

Keywords

Thyroxine Hormone, Post-embryonic Development, Ponderal Index (K) and *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.).

Introduction

Thyroxine hormone plays an important role on growth and protein metabolism of all vertebrates. The phase of metabolism that promotes post-embryonic development, growth along with protein synthesis, by target growth cell is also one among the other descriptions of thyroxine hormone application activity. The effect of thyroxine treatment on the post-embryonic development of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) is not yet fully known and needs further investigation.

Objective of study

With the view point in the present communication an efforts is made to work out the optimum dose of hormone which could be able to affect some aspects of post-embryonic development in a positive direction, as thyroxine treatment has been shown to promote post-embryonic development, growth, ponderal index and survival in several fish species.

Review of Literature

Some of the important contributions on the said field of studies are from Hoar *et. al.* (1955); Lostroh *et. al.* (1958); Scow, R. O. (1959); Ali, M.A.; (1961); Belsare *et. al.* (1966); Yamazaki, F.(1976); Holde *et. al.* (1980); Wilson *et. al.*(1980); Joss, J.M.P. (1985); Blanton *et. al.* (2007); Arjona *et. al.*(2011); Chang *et. al.* (2012); Hamed *et. al.* (2018) and Soheil Alinezhad *et. al.* (2020).

Methodology

The newly hatched larvae (3-4 days old) of *Cirrhina mrigala* (Ham.) were collected from fish farm in the close vicinity of Raebareli. The hatchlings for consecutive development stages were brought to laboratory and transferred to plastic trough under observation. In each experimental trough, 20 specimens were placed on the basis of proper stocking density (Approximately 2 fish/lit.). The physic- chemical conditions of the experimental troughs were maintained merely natural by the use of sand particles, hydrilla plant, zoo and phytoplanktons. Hitachi readymade food

pellets in quantity were also given at regular intervals to all the experimental larvae. The thyroxine hormone (Prolid 0.15mg thyroxine) doses of 75mg/lit., 100mg/lit. and 125mg/lit. concentration were prepared and in each trough one kind of them was added.

By random sampling five specimens from each kind of experiment and control were taken out for derivation of mean standard under different aspects of studies on post- embryonic development at a successive time period 30 days in order to study later developmental stages. Morpho-metrical parameters of the larvae were recorded with the help of Vernier Calipers and weighing balance machine at the end of the experiments.

Ponderal index on the post embryonic development and growth was calculated on the basis of the following equation:-

$$K=W \times 105L^3$$

Where, K =Ponderal index

W = weight of fish

L = Length Of fish

10^5 = Bringing the Pondral index (K) near the unit (Carlander, 1970)

Result and Discussion

On the perusal of the parameters indicated in the Table 1, it can be concluded that a dose 75mg/lit. proved to be the best in term of post-embryonic development (Fig. 1, 2 &Table 1).

Table-1

The general morpho-metrical parameters of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham) larvae revealed that a dose of 75mg/lit., standard length 32.177mm; body length 19.322mm; head length 8.307mm; caudal fin length 2.668; height of the body at anal fin base 6.477mm; height of the body at dorsal fin base 9.282mm; and body weight 114.837mg was observed, which is significant. In terms of the best estimated in correspondence to post-embryonic development.

It has also been marked those early developmental periods when morphogenesis is on it full seeing, the thyroxine treatment resulted into maximum increment in standard body length at 75mg/lit. dose. Survival percentage was maximum in control which gradually decreased at 75mg/lit; 100mg/lit. and 125mg/lit. dose treatment (Table1)

The application of T1 (75mg/lit.) for 30 days duration of the experiment prove to be the best in term of total length in comparison to control and other thyroxine doses.

Ponderal index is calculated for different doses of thyroxine hormone in treatment of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) for 30 days experiment. As Fig. 2 the Ponderal index showed decrement in respect to control sets. The best result in terms of minimum Ponderal index at T1(75mg/lit.) provide the values as 00.344 for 30 days experiment.

S.No.	General Measurement	000mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	75mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	100mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	125mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)
1	Standard Length	21.897 \pm 0.024	32.177 \pm 0.840	27.002 \pm 0.493	27.260 \pm 0.565
2	Body Length	13.397 \pm 0.005	19.322 \pm 0.627	16.707 \pm 0.476	16.043 \pm 0.482
3	Head Length	06.307 \pm 0.018	08.307 \pm 0.233	06.767 \pm 0.313	06.532 \pm 0.441
4	Caudal fin length	02.360 \pm 0.278	02.668 \pm 0.373	02.560 \pm 0.422	02.572 \pm 0.272
5	Height of the body at anal fin base	04.887 \pm 0.054	06.477 \pm 0.507	05.777 \pm 0.479	06.317 \pm 0.523
6	Height of the body at dorsal fin base	06.747 \pm 0.037	09.282 \pm 0.508	07.847 \pm 0.666	07.232 \pm 0.484
7	Body Weight	88.876 \pm 0.486	114.837 \pm 0.493	110.320 \pm 0.289	111.896 \pm 0.495
8	Ponderal index	00.845	00.344	00.560	00.551
9	Mortality	Four	Five	Seven	Twelve

Conclusion

Therefore, 75mg/lit. dose was calculated to be the best effective dose in respect to post-embryonic development and low mortality of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) larvae.

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